

MOBIL ILOVALAR YARATISHDA MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASIDAN FOYDALANISH TEXNOLOGIYALARI

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Ma'lumki, vaqt o'tishi bilan, yangi texnologiyalar asosida ishlaydigan qurilmalar yaratilishi bilan birgalikda ularga yoziladigan dasturiy mahsulotlarga bo'lgan talab kundan kunga ortib bormoqda. Shu jumladan, Android smartfonlariga va tablet kompyuterlarga yoziladigan dasturlar bunga misol bo'laoladi. So'nggi yillarda mamlakatimizda android smartfonlariga ko'plab dasturiy mahsulotlar yaratilib kelinmoqda. Bunga misol qilib o'zbek yoshlarining ushbu sohada egallab kelayotgan yutuqlarini keltirishimiz mumkin. Barchamizga ma'lumki, android operatsion tizimi yaratilishida Linux operatsion tizimining afzallik tomonlaridan eskizlar olingan, ya'ni xavfsizlik, moslashuvchanlik va h.k larni aytib o'tishimiz mumkin. Statistika asosan, 2013 yilga kelib Android operatsion tizimida, iOS va Mac OS tizimlaridan ancha ilgari ketdi. Shu yilning o'zida Android smartfonlarining jahon bozorida tashkil etgan qismi 81.3 foizga yetdi.

Boshqacha qilib aytganda bugungi kunga kelib android smartfonlariga va ularga yoziladigan dasturiy ta'minotlari ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratishga bo'lgan talab kundan kunga ortib bormoqda.

Xususan, SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasidan foydalangan holda dasturiy mahsulotlarni yaratishni asosiy maqsad qilib qo'yishdir.

- ^ veb index
- % mobile internet users
- using the following
- operating systems
- O Android
- O Windows Phone
- O BlackBerry OS
- O Symbian
- O Other

Mobil qurilmalar uchun operatsion tizimlarning qo'llanilish ko'rsatkichlari.

Mobil qurilmalar uchun dasturiy vositalar fanining asosiy maqsadi talabalar uchun mobil ilovalar yaratishning asosiy prinsip lari, qoidalari va ko'nikmalarini hosil qilish bo'lib, yuqorida aytib o'tganimizdek mobil qurilmalar uchun kerakli asosiy komponentadan biri bu SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimidir.

SQLite - bu ochiq kodli ma'lumotlar bazasi hisoblanib, bu relyatsion ma'lumotlar bazasining standart imkoniyatlariga egadir. Bundan tashqari SQLite ma'lumotlar omborida ishlash uchun xotiradan uncha katta bo'lmagan miqdorda joy talab etiladi (taxminan 250 kb). SQLite ni Android OT da ishlatish uchun ma'lumotlar omborini o'ratish va sozlash talab etilmaydi.

SQLite arxitekturasi Bunda ma'lumotlar ombori bilan ishlash uchun faqat SQL so'rovlari amalga oshirish talab etiladi. Demak bu narsa shuni ko'rsatadiki, Ma'lumotlar bazasi va banki fani bocsyicha umumiy ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lgan talaba SQLite dan foydalanish imkoniyatiga

ega bo'ladi. O'z navbatida SQLite obyektga yo'naltirilgan dasturlash asosida yaratilgan bo'lib, barcha ajratilgan modullar uchun maxsus paketlar, sinflar va funksiyalar (metodlar) mavjud. Masalan, android.database - paketi barcha kerakli bo'lgan sinflarni o'z ichiga oladi, android.database.sqlite - paketi SQLite uchun barcha kerakli bo'lgan sinflarni o'z ichiga oladi. O'z navbatida SQLiteOpenHelper, SQLiteDatabase - sinfi ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratish va ishlov berish uchun ishlatiladi. Bundan tashqari maxsus metodlari mavjud:

- insertQ - ma'lumotlar bazasiga ma'lumot yozish
- update () - ma'lumotlar bazasida i yozilgan ma'lumotlarni qayta o'zgartirish
- deleteQ - ma'lumotlarni bazadan o'chirish
- execSQLQ-SQL so'rovni yuklash
- rmvQueryO -jadvalning satr ma'lumotlarni kiritish uchun so'rovni yuklash
- queryQ - kiritilgan so'rovni chaqirish va h.k.lar
- openQ - ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan ishlash uchun oqim hosil qilish
- closeQ — ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan ishlash uchun yaratilgan oqimni yopish

SQLite ni MySQL va boshqa ma'lumotlar omboridan farqi shundan iboratki, MySQL, MS SQL, ORACLE, PostgreSQL laming ishlashi uchun alohida server talab etiladi hamda server - mijoz munosabatini tashkil etish uchun ham oldindan aniqlangan eshituvchi port belgilangan bo'lishi shart, SQL ite ma'lumotlar omborida esa hech qanaqa sender o'rnatilishi talab etilmaydi va turli xil turdagi operatsiyalarni bajarish boshqa ma'lumotlar bazasiga qaraganda ancha oson hisoblanadi.

SQL ite quyidagi turdagi ma'lumotlar toifalari uchun o'rinli hisoblanadi, ya'ni TEXT (Java dasturlash tilidagi String toifaga o'xshash), INTEGER (Java dasturlash tilidagi Long toifaga o'xshash) va REAL (Java dasturlash tilidagi Double toifaga o'xshash).

Bugungi kunga kelib ko'plab smartfonlarga yozilayotgan dasturiy mahsulotlarning ma'lumotlar bazasi ishlab chiqishda SQL ite dan foydalanilyapti. Bunga asosiy sabab qilib, SQLite ning ishlash tezligini olishimiz mumkin hamda ushbu ma'lumotlar bazasi barcha turdagi operatsion tizimlarida bir xilda ishlay oladi. SQLite ma'lumotlar omborida 140 terabayt hajmdagi axborotni saqlash mumkin ya'ni 2 bayt gacha. Darhaqiqat, Android OS sida SQL ite ma'lumotlar omborining ishlash prinsipiga to'xtaladigan bo'lsak, MS SQL ma'lumotlar omboridan foydalanadigan bo'lsak bizga JDBC kerak bo'ladi ya'ni Java Database Connector, lekin Android OS sida ishlaydigan bo'lsak JDBC ni ko'chirib olib o'rnatishni zaruriyati yo'q. Demak, bundan kelib chiqadiki hech qanaqa qo'shimcha driver keragi yo'q. Xulosa qilib aytganda, yuqorida keltirib o'tilganlardan kelib chiqqan holda shuni ayta olamizki, mobil ilovalar uchun ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratish texnologiyalaridan biri bo'lgan SQL ite texnologiyasidan foydalanish bizga qo'shimcha imkoniyatlarni hamda Android smartfonlari uchun bugungi kundagi dolzarb bo'lgan dasturiy mahsulotlarni yaratishda muhim omil bo'lib hisoblanadi

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